

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

DETERMINE THE INCIDENCE OF NECK PAIN IN PEOPLE & ITS IMPACTS ON DAILY ROUTINE ACTIVITIES

Dr. Amina Riaz, Dr. Aafia Khalid, Dr. Zainab Ghazali

DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala

Article Received: February 2019

Accepted: March 2019

Published: April 2019

Abstract:

Objective: This study aimed to determine the incidence of neck pain in people & its impacts on daily routine activities.

Study Design: The design of this study based on observations.

Study Setting: Outpatient department of Mayo Hospital Lahore. This study started in July 2018 & to October 2018.

Major outcome: The pain in neck is the cause of morbidity in both sex which leads to loss of working hours resulting in financial as well as household stress.

Results: Total one hundred patients were the part of this study. Fifty four were male patients and 46 were the women. The range of the age of patients was from 15 to 70 years with an average age of 37.0 ± 15.12 years. The range of pain duration was from 1 to 10 years with average age of 4.0 ± 3.80 years. Total 69.0% patients were living their married life & 31.0% were not married. Total 74.0% patients were from city areas and 26.0% patients found with non-urban background. Total 69.0% patients were performing their jobs in sitting posture & 31.0% patients were working in standing posture with bending their necks during work. There was radiation of the pain towards arms in 53.0% patients; tedious localized in 34.0% patients, stabbing was available in 9.0% patients & flaming character in 4.0% patients. There was no deficiency related to neurology in any patients except the pain during movement which has association with muscle spasm. Muscle relaxants were in use for those patients; our specialist advised them for the exercises of extended muscles & to improve their environment of working with the use of high desks with soft collar. Seventy eight percent patients showed development in pain while 22.0% patients did not get rid of these complications who got referral to other physiotherapists.

Conclusions: The pain in neck & linked pain in the muscle of neck is frequent sign. The prevention of spasm of muscle is possible with good posture; good position of neck while working and hinder to bend the neck for long durations. Relaxants of muscles, NSAIDs & normal extensions with exercises can be helpful in settlements of such complications.

KEY WORDS: Neck, Complication, Flaming, Neurology, Localized, Settlements, Extended, Posture, Radiation.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Amina Riaz,

DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala

QR code

Please cite this article in press Amina Riaz et al., *Determine The Incidence Of Neck Pain In People & Its Impacts On Daily Routine Activities.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(04).

INTRODUCTION:

It is impossible that any person has never faced shoulder or neck pain in his whole life. This pain can have a mild nature and sometimes, it leads to severe complications. The disorders of cervical spine & soft neck tissues are the cause of pain in neck. The pain of neck due to cervical spine can increase with movements and can lead to limit movement of neck [1]. Sometimes, there is confusion when pain starts from the brachial plexus, shoulder nerves or/and peripheral nerves which are easily identifiable & differentiable with elaborated previous history & patient's examination. Unilateral muscular pain or bilateral pain of muscles can be because of muscles spasm due to injury, irregular position during sleeping and long duration of working with neck in bend position. This type of pain is normally self-limiting [2].

Muscular pain has the ability to affect the muscle of trapezius, process of spinous, C7 or all of these issues. If this muscle spasm is for longer durations as for months, this created a shape of chronic pain in the muscles of neck as well as trapeze. Sometimes, it feels like the pain in shoulder girdle. It can have association with headaches, pain transferring from head to temple and pressure on eye ball. Fibromyalgia has the same types of features which cause to create confusion. There should be a proper diagnosis of the neck pain and we can get relieve from this pain by simply correcting the posture as well as exercises. Sometimes, this pain can be extreme which is infective or traumatic and those patients have to go surgery of cervical spine [3].

METHODOLOGY:

This research work is an observational research. This research work conducted in outpatient department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore and its consultant's private chambers. This study started in July 2018 & to October 2018. The method used for sampling of the participants was convenience sampling. The tests of C/E of blood, sugar of blood, uric acid in serum, Rh factor and ANA (Antinuclear Antibodies) carried out when there was requirement. All persons with any age, both genders who appeared with the pain in neck or radiated pain to shoulder were the part of this research work. A standard Performa was in use for the collections of all features. X-ray of the cervical spine AP as well as lateral sight carried out for all the participants. And in some patients, the X-ray of the shoulder joint and sacroiliac joints performed for better examination. All the participants found with hyperuricemia and other malignant conditions of shoulder were not the part of this work.

RESULTS:

A sum of 100 patients was the part of this study. Fifty four percent patients were men & 54.0% patients were female. The range of the age of patients was 15 to 70 years with an average age of 37.0 ± 15.12 years. The range of the period of the pain was from 1 to 10 years with an average duration of 4.0 ± 3.80 years. Total 69.0% patients were enjoying their married life and 31.0% were not married. Total 26.0% patients were from non-urban areas and 74.0% patients were from city regions. There were 42.0% housewives, 28.0% students, 20.0% workers with long work hours & 9.0% laborers and only 1.0% were sportsmen. The work of 69.0% patients was in sitting posture & 31.0% patients were working in standing posture with their bent necks at their duty place. (Table-1)

Table-1 : Sample distribution according to different variables

Variables		Patients (n=100)
Gender	Male	54
	Female	46
Marital Staus	Married	69
	Single	31
Posture with bent neck	Sitting	69
	Standing	31
Background	Urban	74
	Rural	26

The pain was transferring to shoulder and arms in 53.0% patients; tedious localized in 34.0% patients, stabbing present in 9.0% patients and flaming character obtained in 4.0% patients. We did not find any neurological deficiency except painful movement of neck associated with the spasm of muscle. The use of the proper high desks and soft collar were good for neck health. Patients were using relaxants of muscles & exercises of the neck for the prevention of this problem. With the application of these measures, 78.0% patients displayed recovery in the pain but 22.0% patients did not show any relief and they got referrals to physiotherapist.

DISCUSSION:

There are different reasons of pain in neck and almost every person has to suffer this at any time in his life time. People normally visit general practitioners or use self-prescribed medicines. Doctors or physicians come later when the problem is not recovering from other sources. The pain of neck is more frequent in men (54.0%) whereas 46.0% women complained this issue with the average age of 37.4 ± 15.12 years which is working age of the persons. Cervical is the most moveable part of the spine which face the large amount of stress [2]. There is high prevalence of musculoskeletal complications in females but this is not the observation of our study [4]. If there is loss of the working hours, it damages the economic condition as well as activities of the house.

This issue can lead the patients to depression. There are some families in our societies where the elder sisters have to leave the study to handle the works of house because it is impossible for mother to work. The most common place of the pain was lower part of spine cervical, scapular & some region of shoulder which is similar to many other case studies [5-7]. In the same manner, male who are suffering from severe pain have to change their profession to get rid of this issue. About 53.0% patients found with the pain radiating to their left arm. Schoenfeld has concluded that the pain in the upper back & prickly feelings in

the upper region of arm in ultra-sonographers as a professional hazard [8]. Stabbing pain in 9.0% patients causes the patients to reach at hospitals in emergency because of the availability of pressures on the roots [9]. Total 64 patients were working on desks having long working hours in the position with neck bent, and 31.0% patients were available with jobs of standing posture with abnormal position of the neck which was causing the stretching of the muscles of neck.

In most of the patients, the main reasons of the problem were irregular postures, long time driving or lift of heavy weight [10]. Students were also the victims of this issue due to long study hours in irregular postures on chairs during class or exam and use twisted pillow while studying. It is relevant to remember that in all the participants we were not able to find infective for example cervical spine's tuberculosis [11, 12] or expansion of complication to cervical spine in ankylosing spondylitis [13] as stated in this subject where atlantoaxial ossification occur in patients which is the common reason of hindrance in movement & spasm of muscle which is the cause of chronic neck pain.

CONCLUSIONS:

The pains of neck are not because of traumatic or malignant reasons of the cervical spines. When this

pain transfers to the arm or left half of body, it creates a situation of emergency in few patients. The good posture, good postures of neck during working hours are useful to overcome the issue. Light exercises, and muscle relaxants can tackle these issues of neck.

REFERENCES:

1. Lee YN, Kin JI, Park JY, Choe JY. Cervical spine involvement in longstanding ankylosing spondylitis. *Clin Exp Rheumatol* 2005; 23(3): 331-8.
2. Kumar, Clark. *Clinical Medicine* 5th edition W.B. Saunders UK 2003; 518-30.
3. Tamez Gonzalez S. Risks and health problems caused by use of video terminals, *Salud Publica de Mexico* 2003; 45(3):171-80.
4. Koh D, Ong CN, Jeyartanam J. The safe use of visual display units *Singapore Med J* 1994; 35(4): 381-5.
5. Nachemson A, Morris JM. In vivo measurement of intradiscal pressure. *J Bone Joint Surg* 1964; 46 A: 1077.
6. Palmer KT, Cooper C, Walker Bone K. Use of Keyboards and symptoms in the neck and arm: evidence from national survey: *Occup Med (London)* 2001; 51(6): 392-5 Comment in: 51(6): 365-6.
7. Sachoenfeld A, Governmen J, Weiss DM, Meizner I. Transducer user syndrome an occupational hazard of ultrasonographer. *Eur J Ultrasound* 1999; 10(1):41-5.
8. Koffman, B, Junk, L, Elias, SB. Polyradiculopathy in sarcoidosis. *Muscle and Nerve* 1999; 22, 608-13.
9. Maurice RS, Williams. Disorders of spinal nerve. *Concise Oxford Textbook of Medicine* 1st ed, Oxford University Press UK 2000, p 1271-4.
10. Islam N, Ahmedani M. Cervical spine tuberculosis. *J. Coll. Phyc. Surg. Pak.* 2004; 14(8): 499-500.
11. Cassidy JD. Effect of eliminating compensation for pain and suffering on the outcome of insurance claims for whiplash injury. *New Eng J Med* 2000; 342: 1179.
12. Agarwal S, Jain, UK. Management of spinal tuberculosis — current concept review tutorial. *J Indian Med Assoc* 2004; 102(3): 164-9.
13. Mendell JR. Clinical Practice Painful sensory neuropathy. *New Eng J Med* 2003; 348: 1243.